

**Advanced biodiversity monitoring for results-based
and effective agricultural policy and transformation**

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Working definitions of biodiversity

1 Preface

BioMonitor4CAP is a multifaceted project focusing on creating tools and conditions to improve biodiversity outcomes in agriculture. The different workpackages and tasks operate on varied scales and with various biodiversity objectives. To avoid confusion and facilitate understanding within and across the workpackages, common definitions of biodiversity are needed. Such definitions are needed, for example, for understanding and developing biodiversity indicators. The definitions contained herein were collated for the BioMonitor4CAP by project partner University of Helsinki, which has expertise in agroecology and, specifically, research in biodiversity in farmland landscapes.

2 Biodiversity

Biodiversity is defined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) as:

The variability among living organisms from all sources including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are a part. This includes variation in genetic, phenotypic, phylogenetic, and functional attributes, as well as changes in abundance and distribution over time and space within and among species, biological communities and ecosystems.

Note that within this broad definition biodiversity occurs on three levels: genetic, species and habitat or landscape mosaic levels. In developing monitoring tools and ways forward to improve biodiversity outcomes in farmland, BioMonitor4CAP project is primarily concerned with the species and habitat levels. Overall, monitoring takes place on a continuum ranging from general surveillance for measuring trends and providing ad hoc environmental insights to targeted monitoring designed to answer specific hypotheses (Potts et al. 2021). Monitoring is further described in Potts et al. (2021).

There are different approaches to measuring biodiversity, and each comes with its own advantages and shortcomings.

There are three main levels commonly taken into consideration when measuring biodiversity. These are:

- 1) Alpha diversity refers to the number of species (=richness) and evenness (of the abundances between the species) within a functional community;
- 2) Beta diversity refers to the similarity or difference in abundance patterns between two or more communities under comparison, and
- 3) Gamma diversity is the overall species diversity across communities in a biogeographic or political area (e.g. all bird species in a country), usually expressed as richness, i.e. number of species.

Alpha, beta and gamma diversity are further described in Andermann et al. (2022). Potts et al. (2021) use the distinctions of species occurrence, abundance and diversity. Occurrence is the presence or

absence of a species in a particular place at a particular time, and it is particularly important in species, such as pollinators, with stochastic metapopulation dynamics (extinction and colonisation of local populations).

3 Biodiversity in agriculture

'Biodiversity in farmlands' or 'biodiversity in farmland landscapes' refers to all the biodiversity on the farm or within the farmland landscape, respectively. This is a broader definition than the agrobiodiversity definition below.

Agrobiodiversity is defined by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) as:

The variety and variability of animals, plants and micro-organisms that are used directly or indirectly for food and agriculture, including crops, livestock, forestry and fisheries. It comprises the diversity of genetic resources (varieties, breeds) and species used for food, fodder, fibre, fuel and pharmaceuticals. It also includes the diversity of non-harvested species that support production (soil micro-organisms, predators, pollinators), and those in the wider environment that support agro-ecosystems (agricultural, pastoral, forest and aquatic) as well as the diversity of the agro-ecosystems.

Although the diversity of agro-ecosystems is also mentioned at the end, the emphasis is on biodiversity in (positive) relation to agricultural production. FAO considers agrobiodiversity a subset of biodiversity that includes: Mixed agro-ecosystems, crop species and varieties, livestock and fish species, plant and animal germplasm, soil organisms in cultivated areas, biocontrol agents against agricultural pests, wild species as landraces or with breeding, and cultural and local knowledge of diversity.

The narrow definition with emphasis of agrobiodiversity framed in relation to agricultural production is useful for e.g. understanding the provision of ecosystem services by biodiversity (e.g. pollination services by wild pollinators). However, BioMonitor4CAP is concerned with all biodiversity (species) in farmland and farmland landscapes, and this includes species that may not have direct benefit to agricultural production. Thus, the working definition for biodiversity in agriculture for BioMonitor4CAP can be summarized following Helenius (2020, Annex I) as:

- 1) Production diversity: Diversity of production organisms (at genetic and species level) and of agricultural land uses: "agrobiodiversity" in the FAO's narrow definition;
- 2) Serving diversity: Diversity of species and habitats providing farming with ecosystem services;
- 3) Associated wildlife diversity: Diversity of species and habitats associated to agricultural landscapes.

4 Defining biodiversity for stakeholders

BioMonitor4CAP includes tasks and workpackages that communicate with and engage stakeholders in various types of workshops, interviews, and other fora. A simple, easily understood definition of biodiversity is needed, as it will be read aloud in, e.g. personal and group interviews (focus groups). The following definition is intended for use with stakeholders:

Biodiversity encompasses all living and non-living species of animals, plants and other organisms and their genes, and the diversity of habitats in which they live. Biodiversity can be delimited to biodiversity in farmland which, in the broad sense, refers to the number and variety of species on the farm or in the farmland landscape. Agrobiodiversity may also be more narrowly defined as the diversity of species, genes, organisms and landscapes encountered on agricultural areas that contribute to agricultural operations, food production and food security. Agrobiodiversity is co-constructed with nature through a combination of planned agrobiodiversity, i.e. the diversity of food crops and animals such as wheat and cattle; associated agrobiodiversity encompassing wild species that live on and around farmland such as birds, pollinators, natural enemies and wildflowers; and species interactions. The diversity of landscapes creates different habitats and resources for other species. These create functional diversity that support ecological processes in agriculture such as pollination.

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ANNEX 1 Table for Agrobiodiversity, Helenius, Juha 2014. The “3 x 3 table for agrobiodiversity”, inspired by Altieri’s (1999) “The ecological role of biodiversity in agroecosystems”*. Source: Lecture slides of course KTT201_Agroekologia, at Univ. Helsinki., unpublished.

*Altieri, M. (1999) [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809\(99\)00028-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8809(99)00028-6)

"Agrobiodiversity"	Production biodiversity (this is planned and managed diversity)	Serving biodiversity (this can be planned and managed, and enhanced: it is producing ecosystem services)	Associated biodiversity (neutral or dis-serving diversity)
Genetic diversity (within populations & between populations)	Richness and evenness of alleles in the genomes of cultivars and animal breeds	...in the genomes of the serving and regulating species	...in the genomes of the associated species
Species diversity (within a community alpha, of between communities beta)	Richness and evenness of production organisms, and similarities of these across farms	...of serving organisms	...of associated organisms
Ecosystem (habitat) diversity at farm or landscape scale, and over years	Richness and evenness, and similarity of temporal and spatial patterns of uses of farmland	...of (often semi-natural) land or water bodies producing or maintaining services	...of associated habitats existing in the farmscape or agricultural landscape

ANNEX 2 Biodiversity in Agriculture, Juha Helenius 2020. (in the same folder).

AGRI-212 Ecological farming methods

Biodiversity in agriculture

Juha Helenius

1. What is biodiversity?

- at **genetic** level? (within populations)
- at **species** level? (withing communities, across communities, over regions?)
- at **ecosystems** level? (within landscapes)
- loss of biodiversity: **the 6th mass extinction**

2. Species diversity and ecosystem function

- how do you expect ecosystem function is related to diversity of the species producing the function(s)?
- what is functional diversity? (within an ecological community)

3. Land sharing vs. land sparing?

- “Intensify agriculture and increase yields per ha in order to spare land for conserving biodiversity (wildlife, ecosystems)”

vs.

- “Design wildlife-friendly farming so that agricultural landscapes support both biological diversity and agricultural production”

The sharing vs. sparing discussion

- “Sparing”-theorists do not include agrobiodiversity in their equation: diversity of production organisms and organisms that provide essential ecosystem services to production
 - intensifying most often results in loss of ecosystem services
- Sparing theorists do not include the unsustainability of current input-intensive farming in their equation

“Intensify agriculture and increase yields per ha for sparing land for conserving biodiversity”
vs. “Design wildlife-friendly farming so that agricultural landscapes support both biological diversity and agricultural production”

- Will land spared from farming be land spared for nature?
- Trade-offs between food production and nature conservation are obvious, but not simple:

- Increasing yield is rarely associated with reduction of agricultural area
 - Without policy intervention, agriculture may expand further to wild areas
- Jevons' paradox seems to apply: increased economic efficiency of inputs (with price: land, work) result in increased consumption of land through the mechanisms of agribusiness
 - What would have happened without the land use intensification of the conventional farming?

For more of this line of thinking, see: Grau et al. (2013). Beyond 'land sparing versus land sharing'... *Current Opinion in Env. Sustainability* 5: 477-483.

“Intensify agriculture and increase yields per ha for sparing land for conserving biodiversity”
vs. “Design wildlife-friendly farming so that agricultural landscapes support both biological diversity and agricultural production”

- Is better food availability for the global population achieved by increasing yields per ha? (-> how food availability can be increased? What (else) is needed for food security?)

Food (and nutritional) security is through

- (1) availability and
- (2) access/entitlement to, and
- (3) utilization of adequate, nutritious food, and
- (4) stability of these,

for an individual, community or nation for maintenance of active life in dignity. This security must cover all people irrespective of their age, sex, gender, ethnic origin, social status, political opinion, physical or mental condition: across boundaries, within the generation and for the future generations.

“I suggest that the dichotomy of the land-sparing/land-sharing framework limits the realm of future possibilities to two, largely undesirable, options for conservation. Both large, protected regions and favorable surrounding matrices are needed to promote biodiversity conservation; they work synergistically and are not mutually exclusive. A “bothand” framing of large protected areas surrounded by a wildlife-friendly matrix suggests different research priorities from the “either-or” framing of sparing versus sharing. Furthermore, wildlife-friendly farming methods such as agroecology may be best adapted to provide food for the world’s hungry people.”

Claire Kremen (2015. *Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.* 1355 (2015) 52–76.
<https://www.doi.org/10.1111/nyas.12845>)

“Intensify agriculture and increase yields per ha for sparing land for conserving biodiversity”
vs. “Design wildlife-friendly farming so that agricultural landscapes support both biological diversity and agricultural production”

- Does the “sparing” theory represent people-nature dichotomy, while the transformative paths to sustainability need “one nature” thinking in economic and social agendas:

Or, what do you think?

